

DISRUPTIVE TECHNOLOGIES OF ISRAEL AND UNITED STATES OF AMERICA AFFECTING PALESTINE

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ABSTRACT:

This research study examines the use and impact of the disruptive technologies in the battleground, more focused on the Israel-Palestine conflict and the support of USA to Israel has been reached to a more war like situation between 2023 and 2024. Moreover, The study reveals how Israel's advanced surveillance, drone, and artificial intelligence capabilities which are increased by the help of USA, that have enabled asymmetric warfare, humanitarian concerns and very random civilian casualties in the regions of Palestine. The findings in this study highlight the disastrous use of the technologies, need for urgent ceasefire, attention to mitigate the negative consequences of these technologies and ensure a more equitable and just resolution to the conflict. This research aims to contribute a deeper understanding and impacts of disruptive technologies and how the powerful state like US is helping Israel on the regional conflicts.

Keywords: *Israel-Palestine conflict, disastrous use of disruptive technologies, asymmetric warfare, humanitarian concerns, civilian casualt.*

INTRODUCTION:

Disruptive technologies; we can have the idea about the word "technology" and when we get a thought of technology, our minds reach to the thought of "MODERN DIGITAL WORLD". New emerging advanced technologies which are so "beneficial" but also a source of "destruction, damage and devastation. We very well know that technologies like AI, advanced security and surveillance systems often led to enhanced efficiency and improvised services. This is what exactly DISRUPTIVE TECHNOLOGY means. These technologies are reshaping the societies worldwide and becoming a threat to humanity.

In this article, we will together explore and go through the effects of these technologies which are affecting PALESTINE by ISRAEL with the help of US. As we already know that United States of America is an open and strong ally of Israel, helping in the ongoing ISRAEL-PALESTINE conflict.

The Israel-Palestine conflict is an old but still going conflict, which is now converted to a "war state rather than just a "conflict".

This conflict between "Jews, which are Israelis" and "Arabs in Palestine" happening since the 19th century.

Now, when we state that this conflict is no more a conflict but rather a WAR, because the land of Palestine is changed to a war zone, ruined and destructed place in the past recent years.

According to "Al-Jazeera", which is an independent news organisation which keeps up to date on the recent Israel-Palestine issue, worldwide.

It says that, at least "42,847 people have been killed" and "100,544 people are wounded" in missile attacks and air strikes, on the lands of Gaza and Jerusalem since October 7, 2023. Us provides Israel, the advanced military technology including modern defensive and security systems. It also includes system like; Iron dome, which intercepts incoming rockets, drones and advanced reconnaissance systems. These tools enable Israel to monitor Palestinian territories and track militant activities. As US has the most advanced military technology and defence systems. It also has

the biggest armaments making and supply companies, which supplies the weapons and other armaments worldwide. These companies are the source of great economic support to United states.

Due to the strong alliance of Israel and United States, US is giving Israel its diplomatic, economic and military support and supplies its defensive capabilities, technologies, weapons and missiles to Israel, which is directly used against PALESTINE.

Two Research Questions:

How the ongoing current situation of the warfare in middle east would shape the modern global politics?

In this question we will look up to the scenarios and history including the foreign policies In Arab states like Iraq, Syria, Saudi Arabia and the major powers like Russia, united states and Germany. there objectives and foreign policies influence the national and international interest of Palestine and Israel.

The other question that What would be the consequences of the Israel-Palestine conflict, especially in Gaza, and how do these affect public opinion and peace initiatives in the land and globally?

In this question we will examine through critical analysis if the situation ends in a disastrous or peaceful way and how it is influencing the minds of people, nations and states, and what would be the results of Israel legally in international world. what would be the end and peacemaking process, regionally and internationally, all over the world.

THEORIES APPLIED ON THE CONFLICT:

Theoretical framework:

There are two theories which can be applied to the Israel Palestine conflict.

Realism Theory:

The realist approach focuses on absolute power dynamics and keeping the national interest on the frontline.

Israeli perspective on the application of realist theory is that there are many hostile neighbours which are threat to Israel and the security concerns from Non-actor agencies like Hezbollah and Hamas. The main connection of Israel with the realism is that they are keeping their national interest of

having the land on the cause of millions of dead people. Which explains the assumptions of realist school of thought that human nature is bad. That's why Israeli military is not showing any mercy or easier way b tony attacking the million of people in the land which includes new born babies, children and women.

On the other hand, from the perspective of Palestine, this theory could be applied in a way that the Palestinians seek a sense of security and sovereignty. which leads to secure its own territorial land at any cost, especially on the cost of their lives, they are suffering from extreme drastically condition but they are still standing and protecting their land. Trying achieving independence while having regional and international interest.

Social constructivism theory

social constructivism theory can be applied to the ongoing warfare situation happening in Gaza. the main reason is the identity and nationalism that how these both of the states look onto the territory on the basis of their cultural norms.

Israeli historical narrative of returning to the land of Jerusalem. The main point of view the ongoing conflict is continuation of the existential struggle for the survival of Jewish people From the Palestinian perspective, the main purpose is to save the land which is catastrophe related to the religious approaches. Palestinian identity has been shaped by the experience of refugeehood, statelessness, and occupation. This narrative shape the conflict not only as a territorial dispute, but as a fight for liberty, sovereignty, and the right to live freely and independently in their homes and lands.

SUMMARY OF THE ARTICLES ON ISRAEL AND PALESTINE CONFLICT

Shirkah: Journal of Economics and Business
10 (1), 1-19, 2024

This article is about the history of Israel and Palestine that from where all this conflict has started. It began from UN resolution in 1947 to divide the Palestine into two different states, Arab and Jewish. This division led to the current situation of Israel and Palestine which is became more worse than a conflict and rather a genocide. This article is explaining the different aspects of

both the groups and discussing various factors which has intensified the conflict. It also explained the destruction made by Israeli military which has led to significant environmental and psychological damage on humans and Palestinian territory. Furthermore, It discussed the statistics of poverty, unemployment and death tolls increased since then.

Israeli use of technology in Gaza conflict:

[article from The Atlantic times]

This article shows the historical context between Arabs and Jews which led to the ongoing warfare situation in Gaza. This territorial conflict is now more than a conflict. This article also explains the current situation in Gaza and the simultaneous counterattacks between Hamas and Israel.

In this article a phrase is written which is important to notice. That is;" War is War, and the great unavoidable tragedy of war is civilian death, But unavoidable is not synonymous with Purposeful.

This article further explains that the strategy of Israeli campaign which is subjected to the violence of Palestinian civilians. Moreover, It is also showing the developments and resolutions which are being made by United nations for the humanitarian aid including health facilities in Gaza. It also tells the statistics of death toll of diplomatic peoples and the media persons.

Furthermore , It also showed the expression of black people in America to stop shipping the US weapons to Israel and start giving the humanitarian help and aid , the people of Gaza needs. Different cultures, colour and ethnics are supporting the people of Gaza while living in the west countries, they are standing up against their on-government systems like USA, they people are coming out on the roads in the support of Palestinian people, seeking justice for them and stand against the genocide by Israel.

Use of disruptive technologies in Gaza and Lebanon by Israel:

[article from Al-Jazeera]

This article explains the attacks of Israeli forces and the strong surveillance security systems used by Israel.

After Gaza, Israel is also attacking in Lebanon. Analysts says that this is the new

chapter in the decades-old conflict between the two sides of a land. Hezbollah and Israel have been engaged in a low-level conflict since Israel launched an assault on Gaza which has killed more than 41,000 people using the military forced, missiles and drones.

According to Israeli forces it is difficult to counter attack on Hamas and Hezbollah on land so they are attacking the communication and security surveillance systems through cyberattacks.

Therefore, this article showed the applications of security strategies against Palestine and Lebanon previewing the increased frequency of cyberwarfare which became critically important for Israeli military forces and Political leader.

Emergence of technology in warfare against Gaza:

<https://lieber.westpoint.edu/>

This article shows the emergence of technologies in the warfare against Gaza. It explains that how the use of these technologies is violating IHL, International humanitarian law. Especially the use of artificial intelligence, a decision support tool in targeting the particular target.

Moreover, this article explains the rise of AI in military technological operations and its application in Gaza. AI marks a significant shift in modern warfare tactics and strategies. It explains the use of AI in Israeli drones, satellites equipped with advanced sensors and imaging technologies, which can easily identify and track targets, assess the terrain and monitor the opponent movement.

Furthermore, this article explains different aspects of UN and developmental organisations that what are the measures of transparency in war, and the stance of US in reference to Israel support and shipping the modern technology and surveillance systems to Israel against Palestine.

It wholly explains the limitations, principles and violations of technology in the warfare by giving the most recent case study of ISRAEL-PALESTINE WAR.

How this conflict is shaping the global politics:

<https://foreignpolicy.com/2024/01/05/gaza-war-impact-global-politics-2024-israel-hamas/>

This article shows the neutral aspect between both the states that how an attack by Hamas on oct 7,2023 and a military response in Gaza strip would lead to a disastrous current scenario in Palestine.

Not only just Israel and Palestine having effects of the war but also the world is facing the effects of it.

Globally, people are expressing solidarity with one or the other side of the land of Palestine. It is showing that war has significantly raised tensions all over the world but especially in middle east. The battlefield is not just limited to Gaza strip but expanded to Lebanon, Iraq, Syria and red sea.

The effects of the war have been felt all around the world, leading to multiple battles of ideology, identity, cyberwarfare, media propaganda, multiple debates and with intense diplomatic debates in the united nations and a surge in hate crimes against Arabs, Muslims and Jews.

Furthermore, this article explains the foreign policy being shaped by the world major powers like US and India, discussing that how the elections in US were not based on the issue and how US is supporting Israel as the US former president Joe Biden stated that he is a "Zionist in his heart".

India and the BJP party led by Narinder modi were fanning the flames of Islamophobia in all over the world, found a stance against Islam and relating the Hamas attack on Israel with fake terrorism approach of Islam.

DISCUSSION

the use of disruptive technologies

As cyber conflict advances, the concept of 'hybrid warfare' emerges, blending kinetic and non-kinetic (i.e. digital) operations on the modern battlefield. While traditionally cyber operations have been non-kinetic, a shift in the warfare started, as cyber-attacks on vital infrastructure – like power plants – have the potential to yield tangible, kinetic outcomes that disrupt local operations, and can lead to extensive chaos and collateral damage. With non-state actors increasingly

engaging in disruptive operations, it is observed that the use of this shift is also happening in the ongoing conflict between Israel and Gaza.

October 14, 2023: Cyber Av3nger, a hacking company announce that they have compromised ORPAK, a company that provides payment and management solutions for fuel, retail and fleet businesses in Israel. This was followed by them leaking CCTV footage and data from multiple gas stations and screenshots of the internal panels. The Israeli-Palestinian conflict saw a significant escalation in cyber attacks by hacktivist groups and threat actors from various regions, targeting government websites, education and media sector, billboards, power plants, alert systems, and even sensitive military information. The involvement of these cyber actors added a new dimension to the ongoing conflict, highlighting the vulnerability of nations to cyberattacks in times of elevated tensions. As the situation began to unfold, it became clear that cybersecurity would play a critical role in this complex and long-standing conflict.

(threats, 2023)

Israel's Military Tech Dilemma: The Gaza Conflict's High-Tech Pitfalls

The conflict in the Gaza Strip has surfaced critical vulnerabilities in Israel's military strategy, specifically its heavy reliance on high-tech warfare. Israel's historical emphasis on technological superiority faced unforeseen challenges during the recent conflict, sparking widespread discussions about the sudden disappearance of Israel's advanced military technology and the repercussions of this on the outcome of the conflict.

Israel's robust technological advancements have been a hallmark of its military doctrine, with significant investments in cutting-edge defence systems, cyber capabilities, and sophisticated weaponry. This prowess has been highlighted globally, positioning Israel as a leader in innovation and technology-driven military strategies. However, the recent conflict in Gaza has shed light on the limitations and drawbacks of this approach. The Palestinian resistance, armed with comparatively simpler and less technologically advanced weaponry,

managed to disrupt, and inflict considerable damage on Israel's forces. This raised serious concerns within Israel's defence circles, challenging the assumption that technological superiority alone guarantees military dominance. Amid the conflict, Israel appeared to revert to more traditional military tactics, supplementing advanced technologies with older military equipment and ground deployments. However, even the latest advancements, such as the Eitan armoured personnel carrier and the Rafael's Trophy active protection system, experienced critical failures. Additionally, Israeli air defences struggled to intercept the barrage of rockets fired from Gaza, exposing vulnerabilities despite the deployment of advanced defence systems like the Iron Dome. While Israel is regarded as one of the world's most potent military forces, a disproportionate focus on high-tech solutions might compromise its ability to effectively counter unconventional adversaries like Hamas. This excessive focus on technological superiority might steer policymakers away from crucial decisions in military strategy formulation. Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu's trust in technological solutions, epitomised by the "smart" border fence along Gaza, may have instilled a false sense of security, diverting resources from conventional ground defences, and rendering Israel more susceptible to recent attacks.

Over-reliance on High-Tech Warfare: Israel's historical emphasis on technological superiority faced challenges during the recent conflict in Gaza. The conflict revealed vulnerabilities in their heavy reliance on advanced technology for military dominance.

Limitations of Technological Supremacy: The conflict showed that despite Israel's innovative technology, the Palestinian resistance managed to disrupt and inflict considerable damage on Israel's forces using comparatively simple weaponry.

Communication and Adaptability Concerns: Extensive technological evolution in Israel's forces disrupted communication and decision-making processes on the ground, potentially hampering the adaptability and critical thinking skills of soldiers.

(Badawi, 2024)

Israel AND HAMAS, THE Algorithms of War: Military AI and the War in Gaza

the use of emerging technologies in the Gaza war deserves careful attention. The territories occupied by Israel since 1967 have long been a "proving ground" for new surveillance technologies with the potential to supercharge weapons of war. Independent studies of these technologies are vital to ensure that those technologies that intrinsically violate IHL, or whose uses are inherently harmful, do not perpetuate. The concern is one of "sticky precedent," sustained through a process of gradual toleration and collective silence. The worry is that these technologies and their associated wartime practices will get exported through the arms trade and military aid, thereby transiting from one battle zone to others.

The rise of AI in military applications, particularly in battlefield scenarios, marks a significant shift in modern warfare tactics and strategy. AI's integration into military technology has been driven by its ability to process and analyse large volumes of data rapidly, make predictions, and execute complex tasks with speed and precision that far surpass human capabilities. For instance, in reconnaissance and surveillance, AI-powered drones and satellites are employed for gathering real-time intelligence. These systems, equipped with advanced sensors and imaging technologies, can identify and track targets, assess terrain, and monitor enemy movements with astonishing accuracy. The U.S. military's Project Maven, initiated to automate the analysis of vast amounts of video footage, exemplifies this application. A recent U.S. Department of Defence (DoD) Adoption Strategy accelerated even further "the adoption of advanced data, analytics, and artificial intelligence technologies" in order to increase "rapid, well-informed decision making" by DoD leaders and warfighters alike. The staggering number of civilian casualties and the level of civilian destruction in the war in Gaza, notwithstanding Hamas's historic failure to comply with its obligation to take precautions to protect the civilian population from attacks (which others term human shielding), generates a strong prima facie claim that Israel's AI tools are not currently

calibrated with the aim of minimising harm to civilians and civilian objects. Putting aside lay claims that these AI tools have given rise to a “mass assassination factory,” their use as manifested in Gaza puts into question whether military AI could ever be deployed in a manner protective of IHL rules. As some scholars have argued, “AI-enabled targeting systems, fixed as they are to the twin goals of speed and scale, will forever make difficult the exercise of morally and legally restrained violence.” (Omar Yousef Shehabi, 2024)

Us Intervention in the conflict:

The Abraham accords were a series of bilateral agreements normalising relations between Israel and Morocco, Bahrain, the United Arab Emirates, and Sudan. Critics noted that the accords did relatively little to advance the cause of peace because none of the participating Arab governments were actively hostile to Israel or capable of harming it. Others warned that regional peace would remain elusive as long as the fate of the 7 million Palestinians living under Israeli control was unresolved. The Biden administration continued along much the same path. It took no meaningful steps to stop Israel’s increasingly far-right government from backing violent actions by extremist settlers, which led to a surge in Palestinian deaths and displacements over the past two years. After failing to fulfil a campaign promise to immediately rejoin the JCPOA, Biden and Co. focused their main efforts on persuading Saudi Arabia to normalise relations with Israel in exchange for some sort of U.S. security guarantee and perhaps access to advanced nuclear technology.

The motivation for this effort had little to do with Israel-Palestine, however, and was mostly intended to keep Saudi Arabia from moving closer to China. Linking a security commitment to Saudi Arabia with normalisation was primarily a way to overcome U.S. congressional reluctance to a sweetheart deal with Riyadh. Like Israeli Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu and his cabinet, top U.S. officials appear to have assumed that there was nothing that any Palestinian group could do to derail or slow this process or draw attention back to their plight.

As the Russian president Vladimir Putin “Just look at the Middle East,” they might say. “The United States has been managing the region by itself for more than three decades, and what has its ‘leadership’ produced? We see devastating wars in Iraq, Syria, Sudan, and Yemen. Lebanon is on life support, there is anarchy in Libya, and Egypt is lurching toward collapse. Terrorist groups have morphed and mutated and sown fear on several continents, and Iran keeps edging closer to the bomb. There is no security for Israel and neither security nor justice for the Palestinians. This is what you get when you let Washington run everything, my friends. Whatever their intentions may have been, U.S. leaders have repeatedly shown us that they lack the wisdom and objectivity to deliver positive results, not even for themselves.”

(Walt, 2018)

THE 3 ENTITIES

The USA:

U.S. decisions, which are completely divorced from the official U.S. policy of supporting a two-state solution, have meant aiding an expansionist Israeli state as it seeks to impose its exclusionary territorial vision on the Palestinian people. These decisions have also left an administration with a foreign policy record in the Middle East that has been heavily reliant on military means. U.S.-manufactured weapons, whose export to Israel’s armed forces has been approved and often funded by the U.S. government, have been key to mass Israeli killing and societal destruction in Gaza. Israel’s military has killed at least 42,000 Palestinians in Gaza, with over 95,000 wounded, and some estimates are much higher. The United States has tremendous potential leverage over Israel, but it has largely chosen not to use it. There are a number of competing explanations as to why the United States has chosen not to employ its leverage. U.S. officials may feel they are unable to use U.S. leverage to restrain Israeli military decision making, or maybe they have chosen not to do so because they have sympathy for Israel’s war effort after the brutality of the October 7 attack. Washington may also view Israel as the leading instrument for weakening Iran and its regional allies like Hamas and Hezbollah

— both designated as Foreign Terrorist Organisations by the United States.

The Biden Policies: the Biden administration's policy toward Israel since the Gaza conflict began. It first examines relevant goals that the Biden administration had stressed before taking office: reaching a two-state solution, reducing the military emphasis of U.S. policy in the Middle East, and weakening Iran. It then delves into the expansionist, territorial aim of the current Israeli government, especially its annexation of the West Bank and its deep commitment to the settlement project. The brief then reviews the many different facets of U.S. policy toward Israel-Palestine over the past year. It concludes by emphasising the negative impact these policies have had on the stated goals of the Biden administration. The Biden administration has provided Israel with comprehensive military and diplomatic support in conducting its war in Gaza. This support has continued unabated despite the Israeli government's clear violations of U.S. and international law, thwarting of diplomatic talks, and continued expansion of settlements in the West bank.

At almost every turn during the war, the U.S. government has aided Israel's war effort and thereby bolstered the underlying Israeli strategic goal of annexation rather than territorial compromise. The United States armed Israel, failed to use its leverage to influence Israeli policy as Israel repeatedly rebuffed U.S. entreaties, shielded Israel from U.S. laws that Israel had likely violated, protected Israel at the U.N. Security Council, emphasised Israeli self-defence while disregarding Israel's expansionist motives, and completely failed in ensuring that Palestinians in Gaza received adequate humanitarian aid. The U.S. military has also been drawn into fighting, such as the bombing of Houthi forces in Yemen and shooting down Iranian missiles targeting Israel. For example, on October 31, 2023, Israel dropped a U.S.-made 2,000-pound bomb on residential buildings in the Jabalia refugee camp, killing 120. On January 9, 2024, an Israeli plane dropped a U.S.-made Boeing GBU-39 bomb on a residential building, killing 18. On May 13, 2024, Israel used the same type of U.S.-made bomb on a school serving as a shelter, killing approximately 30. On June 6, 2024, Israel

dropped GBU-39 bombs on the al-Sardi school in Nusreit, also serving as a shelter for displaced families, killing 40. On June 23, 2024, Israel fired a U.S.-made Hellfire missile at a health clinic in Gaza City.

As a result, the Biden administration has undercut two of its stated objectives for the Middle East: a two-state solution and a reduction in the regional U.S. military footprint. The Biden government has also pursued a third goal, the mitigation of Iranian threats to U.S. interests, allies, and partners in the region.

United States vetoed three U.N. Security Council resolutions calling for a ceasefire (October 18, 2023; December 8, 2023; and February 20, 2024).⁴⁹ Even after it abstained on U.N. Security Council Resolution 2728 on March 25, 2024, Linda Thomas-Greenfield, U.S. ambassador to the United Nations, immediately undermined the U.S. abstention by erroneously calling the resolution “nonbinding.”⁵⁰ Vetoing resolutions that the government of Israel opposes is common U.S. practice; the United States has vetoed resolutions pertaining to negative Israeli conduct over 40 times. United States has generally used its aircraft carriers to deter Iranian involvement in the war, but there have also been specific engagements involving U.S. forces. For example, in April 2024, the United States and its allies “shot down the majority of Iranian drones and cruise missiles” targeting Israel.

The unconditional U.S. assistance and diplomatic cover. The United States has armed Israel, failed to use its leverage to influence Israeli policy as Israel repeatedly rebuffed U.S. requests, shielded Israel from U.S. laws that Israel had likely violated, protected Israel at the U.N. Security Council, disregarded Israel's efforts to expand its territory in ways that undermine any possible two-state solution to the Israel-Palestine question, and failed to ensure that Palestinians in Gaza received adequate humanitarian aid.

ISRAEL:

the Israeli government's initial fighting was driven by defence against the Hamas attack of October 7, 2023, the war is also based on the driving premise of Israeli territorial policy: the settlement and annexation of the

West Bank. Prior to the October attack, the Israeli government viewed maintaining Hamas as a key tool in thwarting a two-state solution — both in terms of Hamas’ aims and the way its presence undermined a unified Palestinian push for independence. The Netanyahu government is highly unlikely to pursue political pathways and diplomatic off-ramps that jeopardise its complete hold on the West Bank. Israeli government is committed to annexing the West Bank. With the 2018 Nation-State Law, Israel cemented its belief that there is only one claim to the Holy Land: the claim of the Jewish people. This strongly implies the Palestinian claim has no standing. When this Israeli government took office in December 2022, its non-binding guidelines delineated the geography of that claim, including what it calls the West Bank, Judea and Samaria: “The Jewish people have an exclusive and inalienable right to all parts of the Land of Israel. The government will promote and develop the settlement of all parts of the Land of Israel.

Although the spotlight has been on Gaza, Israel also has been prioritising expansionist policies on the ground in the West Bank. Governmental and non-governmental Israeli actors have been extremely active in the West Bank over the past year, even with the fighting in Gaza. They have been driving Palestinians from their communities, seizing land, expanding Israeli settlements, invading Palestinian cities, destroying infrastructure, and attacking militants, over the past year, Israeli forces have destroyed Gaza. It is uninhabitable, yet millions of Palestinian people remain in desperate humanitarian circumstances, having been displaced from their homes. Most of those homes are damaged or destroyed. Hundreds of thousands of Palestinians are dead, wounded, or missing. Israel has destroyed every major infrastructural system — communications, electricity, food distribution, medical care, sewage treatment, transport, and water treatment. Rebuilding will probably take generations. The war has presented an opportunity for Israel to crush one societal and territorial pillar of a future Palestinian state, Gaza, and Palestinian life there.

The Israeli forces caused major destruction in Rafah. U.S. officials said, “the offensive

in Rafah was carried out with much more precision than Israel’s other operations in Khan Younis and Gaza City.” But in early July 2024, when the Israeli military brought foreign reporters on a supervised visit into Rafa, The Wall Street Journal reported it was “a flattened wasteland” where “building after building had been reduced to piles of rubble. Israel attacked all 36 hospitals in Gaza.

By January 2024, 59% percent of hospitals’ bed capacity “had been lost.” Euro-Med Monitor reported that the Israeli military had killed 2,100 Palestinian children under the age of two. In December 2023, UNICEF concluded: “The Gaza Strip is the most dangerous place in the world to be a child.” In November 2023, U.N. Secretary-General Antonio Guterres said, “We are witnessing a killing of civilians that is unparalleled and unprecedented in any conflict since I have been secretary-general.” Israel justified its actions by pointing to Hamas operating in and around facilities in urban areas.

(Pressman, 2024)

THE PALESTINE:

The Gaza Strip is a 41km (25-mile) long and 10km-wide territory between Israel, Egypt and the Mediterranean Sea. It was part of a proposed Arab state under the original UN partition plan in 1947. Gaza was the occupied by Egypt in the war that followed Israel's creation, then captured by Israel during the 1967 Six-Day War.

Israel withdrew its troops and about 7,000 settlers from the territory in 2005, though the UN still considers the land to be occupied. Even before the current war between Israel and Hamas, the territory had one of the highest unemployment rates in the world, with most of its population living below the poverty line and depending on food aid to survive. Israel controls Gaza's airspace, its shoreline and the shared border. It also limits the movement of people and goods.

Hamas started as an offshoot of the Muslim Brotherhood in 1987. Its name means Islamic Resistance Movement.

It is opposed to the existence of Israel on what it says is Palestinian land. It wants a state based on Islam in its place and across the occupied West Bank, East Jerusalem and Gaza.

It has, however, sign allied its willingness to accept an interim Palestinian state in just the West Bank, East Jerusalem and Gaza, without renouncing its claim to all of historic Palestine.

Hamas has been the sole ruler in the Gaza Strip since 2007, after winning Palestinian elections and violently ousting rivals. Its most prominent leaders now include Khaled Meshaal, who heads Hamas's relations with Palestinian communities abroad and lives in Qatar, and Mahmoud Zahar, one of the group's founders, who lives in Gaza.

In 2000, sparked in part by Palestinian grievances over Israel's control over the West Bank, a stagnating peace process, and former Israeli Prime Minister Ariel Sharon's visit to the al-Aqsa mosque—the third holiest site in Islam—in September 2000, Palestinians launched the second intifada, which would last until 2005. In response, the Israeli government approved the construction of a barrier wall around the West Bank in 2002.

Hamas's most important allies are Iran - its biggest backer in terms of funds, weapons and political support - and Syria and Qatar. Hamas has also said the attack was a reaction to what it claims are Israeli efforts to take over the al-Aqsa mosque compound in Jerusalem - Islam's third holiest site. Hamas also wants the release of thousands of Palestinians in Israeli prisons.

The year leading up to the attack was also the deadliest in the occupation of the West Bank, since the UN began recording in 2005. By the end of the year at least 505 Palestinians had been killed there, mostly by Israeli soldiers and settlers. In the same year, 30 Israelis were also killed in the West Bank. All Palestinian factions and parties oppose Israel's presence in the West Bank, as well as occupied East Jerusalem and the Gaza Strip. They want the land to be part of a future independent state, something backed by the vast majority of the international community. (BBC,2023)

In the summer of 2014, clashes in the Palestinian territories precipitated a military confrontation between the Israeli military and Hamas in which Hamas fired nearly three thousand rockets at Israel, and Israel retaliated with a major offensive in Gaza. The skirmish ended in late August 2014 with a cease-fire deal brokered by Egypt, but only

after 73 Israelis and 2,251 Palestinians were killed. After a wave of violence between Israelis and Palestinians in 2015, Palestinian President Mahmoud Abbas of Fatah announced that Palestinians would no longer be bound by the territorial divisions created by the Oslo Accords. In March of 2018, Israeli troops killed 183 Palestinians and wounded 6,000 others after some Palestinians stormed the perimeter fence between the Gaza Strip. After the attack of October 7, Israel ordered more than one million Palestinian civilians in northern Gaza to evacuate ahead of a ground invasion that began on October 27th. The ground invasion began in the north in conjunction with Israel's continued aerial assault. The first stage of the ground invasion ended on November 24 with the hostage-for-prisoner swap that also allowed more aid into Gaza. After seven days, the war resumed—particularly in Khan Younis, the largest city in southern Gaza that Israel claims is a Hamas stronghold. Gaza is desperately low on water, fuel, and supplies as Hamas has rejected the most recent cease-fire proposals mediated by the United States and Egypt, while Israel has limited the amount of aid that can enter. Many humanitarian agencies suspended their operations after Israel killed seven World Centre Kitchen employees in an airstrike. The World Food Program warns famine is now imminent in Gaza. Only eleven out of thirty-five hospitals in the strip remain partially functional due to attacks on medical infrastructure and a lack of basic supplies. The World Health Organisation has warned of disease spread in addition to mounting civilian casualties. The displacement of millions more Palestinians presents a challenge for Egypt and Jordan, which have absorbed hundreds of thousands of Palestinians in the past but have resisted accepting anyone during the current war. They fear that Gaza's, many of whom were already displaced from elsewhere in Israel, will not be allowed to return once they leave. Egypt also fears that Hamas fighters could enter Egypt and trigger a new war in the Sinai by launching attacks on Israel or destabilising the authoritarian regime of Abdel Fattah el-Sisi by supporting the Muslim Brotherhood. So far, negotiations have resulted in only 1,100 people exiting Gaza through the Rafah border crossing to

Egypt. The other 1.5 million displaced Gazans—70 percent of the territory's population remained confined to southern Gaza and face increasingly dire living conditions and security. (tracker, 2024)

ANSWERS OF THE RESEARCH QUESTIONS:

How the ongoing current situation of the warfare in middle east would shape the modern global politics?

It has been over a year since the Hamas-led attack on Israel. Israel's response in Gaza has resulted in widespread destruction and significant loss of life. The conflict has since expanded beyond Gaza, involving the Houthis in Yemen, Hezbollah in Lebanon and Iranian strikes targeting Israel.

In addition to the awful humanitarian cost of the conflicts, the war and the possibility of its further expansion pose significant repercussions for the global economy. This article discusses three potential ways in which the current conflict and a wider conflict in the Middle East could affect the global economy.

In response to Israel's actions against its neighbours, the Organisation of the Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC) could reduce oil production to penalise countries supporting Israel. A similar action in the 1970s led to a significant jump in oil prices, which contributed to years of stagflation, with higher global inflation and recessions in major economies.

Before Israel's attack on Lebanon at the end of September, oil prices had been declining due to falling demand, particularly from China. On the supply side, oil production had increased in Canada and the United States, countering the production cuts by OPEC, and Saudi Arabia was expected to increase oil production from December. But the situation quickly reversed following Israel's attack on Lebanon. Oil prices jumped by nearly \$10 per barrel within a week, before easing by around \$5 per barrel. While the immediate oil price impact of Israel's attack has mostly faded, the potential for higher oil (and other energy) prices still poses a risk to global inflation and economic activity (Liadze et al, 2022).

Apart from the significant economic implications, an increase in the diverse conflicts of Middle East that can activate

displacements of people on a very large scale, which may upsurge economic and social pressures on neighbouring countries. Many countries may also have to increase their military expenditure by giving response to increased regional tensions. Given that public debt levels are already elevated in many countries due to successive shocks to the global economy over the past decade, any additional defence spending could come at the expense of public infrastructure investments that would otherwise boost productivity growth.

The greater geopolitical risk has a significantly negative impact on business and consumer confidence in several advanced economies (de Wet, 2023).

What would be the consequences of the Israel-Palestine conflict, especially in Gaza, and how do these affect public opinion and peace initiatives in the land and globally?

There is high chance of regional destabilisation, region immediate neighbours especially Egypt Jordan Lebanon. So Israel is floating idea of Palestinians in Gaza being transferred to Sinai. Egypt and other countries of the region, the EU oppose EU suppression of those being forced out. Even the United States has said this kind of move is not acceptable. Jordan too is very worried about the possibility of Palestinians being forcibly moved from West Bank to Jordan. This is in case Israel would do such thing, it would threaten the peace treaties with Egypt and Jordan on one hand, and would have serious implications regarding a return to direct confrontation between Israeli and Palestinian population in the region. Given the likely catastrophic ramifications of an action like this, multiple states (most notably the US, Egypt and Jordan) up until now have been in near constant and open dialogue to stop population transfer and for Israel to ease its grip on the situation by ceasing ground operations and conducting limited military offensives against Hamas.

the Israeli war cabinet will likely continue the conflict for several more months purposefully saying it aims to destroy and eliminate Hamas. But then there is the divide itself, worsened by multi-faceted issues like Israel bickering, Netanyahu leadership questions; no major military successes in northern southern Gaza and rocket firings directed at Tel Aviv that show

Hamas is still operational and kicking. With the growing Palestinian civilian casualties and the performance on Gaza (international criminal violations as well human rights crimes), the US and some European states unconditional support for Israel is beginning to fall by the wayside.

Hamas survives but as a weaker organisation, this would probably have taken leverage from Iran in the region. It could also nudge thousands of Muslim young men to support Iran and its friends in the region. The assertiveness and influence of Iran's allies, especially in Lebanon, Iraq and Yemen could grow more. Or, if Hamas is obliterated (not likely), Iran may yet win out as many will rally to the Iranian ideology as if it is the only bastion of resistance against the predatory Arab regimes in power. The win or lose card is pretty clear in Gaza for Iran. The future of West Bank is also largely bleak as settler violence in Israel has increased over the past year or so. Recently months on this violence has met with condemnation from most states and international organisations .e UN,EU, US etc as terrorist assaults In the last few months "terrorism" Given the reality of more than 700,000 Israeli settlers in the Occupied and continuing expansion of settlements, it is impossible in absolute terms to have a Palestinian state. In recent years, the level and violence of Israeli settler attacks in the West Bank against Palestinians of an extent never seen before, all too well armed and with their backing coming from Israel most right-wing government ever existed The spike in settler violence and daily military operations of Israel, including the arrests of least tens of thousands Palestinians since October 7 and the destruction of infrastructure all have raised an immediate Palestinian uprising in West Bank settler targets.

A public uprising like this would, no doubt be responded to with a serious military response by Israel (possibly very destructive) and could spell disaster for the PA's grip on the areas where it has any degree of security or administrative control.. (Alijla, 2023)

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, the Israel-Palestine conflict has been significantly and complicatedly impacted through disruptive technologies,

such as drones and advanced surveillance systems. These modernised tools have changed and transformed military operations, Leading to destruction and . the unbothered killings of people. Israel utilises these technologies to enhance its military capabilities, Palestinian groups have also adapted them for their own purposes. This shift in the conflict raises serious concerns about the humanitarian crisis in Gaza and the impact on civilian population. The ongoing conflict in Gaza, which initiated on October 7, 2023, has led to a devastating and drastic humanitarian crisis. The violence began when Hamas, a militant group in Gaza, launched a surprise attack on Israel, resulting in the deaths of over 1,200 people, marking one of the deadliest days for Israel in decades. In the response to the attack, Israel initiated the process of extensive airstrikes and attacked a ground invasion of Gaza, leading to a significant increase in casualties on both sides.

As of January 2025, the situation in Gaza has become dire, with reports indicating that more than 43,000 Palestinians have lost their lives due to the ongoing conflict. The airstrikes and military operations have caused widespread destruction, displacing millions and leaving many without access to basic necessities like food, clean water, and medical care. Hospitals are overwhelmed, and humanitarian aid is urgently needed to address the suffering of civilians caught in the crossfire The international efforts to broke a ceasefire have faced challenges due to the ongoing violence and the high civilian death. While there have been some temporary pauses and periods in fighting, cross attacking and limited hostage exchanges, a lasting resolution is still unrest and missing. The global world including different communities are calling for humanitarian assistance and the protection of civilians, their basic needs and rights, emphasising the need for a diplomatic solution to end the violence

By summarising the article, it is evident that the conflict in Gaza has resulted in immense human suffering and a critical humanitarian crisis. The urgent need for humanitarian aid and a peaceful, peace making resolution is needed. as the situation continues to deteriorate. It is essential for all parties involved to prioritise the safety and well-

being of civilians and work towards a sustainable peace that addresses the underlying issues of the conflict.

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